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From real-driving emissions to urban air quality: composition of aged PM from modern diesel, gasoline, and CNG fueled cars and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles

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ABSTRACT

Secondary aerosol emissions from vehicle exhaust often surpass primary particle emissions, yet they are not currently regulated, as they remain difficult to constrain. Here we investigate the factors driving the formation and chemical composition of secondary aerosol from light-duty vehicle exhaust emissions, focusing on the most recent Euro emission standard (Euro 6d), and including hybrid and natural gas cars.

Seven modern cars were driven through a real-driving emission simulation cycle in a chassis dynamometer. The exhaust emissions were aged in a PAM chamber and their chemical and physical properties measured with an aerosol mass spectrometer and state-of-the-art instrumentation.

Results indicate that secondary aerosol emissions surpassed fresh aerosol emissions for all cars, except for old Euro 4 diesel. While on average, Euro 6d gasoline and diesel cars aged PM emissions were about 90 % lower than emissions from older cars, their cold start emissions were still significant. Hybrid cars also emitted considerably when switching to combustion engine, which, depending on the length and style of the driving, could be comparable to non-hybrid vehicles emissions. Aged organic aerosol was dominated by oxidized compounds typical of ambient secondary organic aerosol, with unique compositions across vehicle types and fuels. Notably, the CNG vehicle emitted hydrocarbon-like organics, likely originating from less reactive species from lubricant oil, and the Euro 4 diesel exhibited organic nitrate formation, an underreported component in vehicle exhaust with atmospheric implications. Secondary aerosol and its precursors should be regulated and considered in reduction technologies, to best mitigate atmospheric PM in urban traffic-influenced areas.

1. Introduction

Vehicles are one of the most important anthropogenic catalysts for air pollution, intensifying the exposure to harmful pollutants across numerous inhabited regions of the world. A wide array of exhaust and non-exhaust pollutants including particulate and gaseous compounds are emitted by vehicular traffic (Harrison et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2020; Rönkkö and Timonen, 2019). Particulate exhaust emissions of vehicles are typically composed of a complex mixture of chemical constituents

such as black carbon (BC), organic compounds (e.g. polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)), inorganic ions and salts (e.g. sulphate, nitrate, and ammonium), and elements (e.g. metals) (Gordon et al., 2014a; Saarikoski et al., 2024; Timonen et al., 2017). In the atmosphere these exhaust compounds might further react with atmospheric pollutants and oxidants forming secondary aerosol (SecA) mass. Secondary aerosol is a major pollution component in cities, increasing PM_{2.5} (particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter of less than 2.5 μm) concentrations and driving haze events (Guo et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2014), as

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well as impacting the climate (Shrivastava et al., 2017). Exposure to PM_{2.5} has also been linked to respiratory diseases, cardiovascular diseases, and neurological disorders (Sangkham et al., 2024). Therefore, traffic emissions have deleterious impacts on both climate and human health (Kostenidou et al., 2021; Bahreini et al., 2012; Chirico et al., 2010), which highly depend on their chemical composition.

Due to environmental and health concerns, substantial research dedicated to diesel and gasoline vehicular emissions has been conducted, leading to cleaner vehicle technologies with more efficient internal combustion engines and improved aftertreatment systems. In earlier models, diesel cars used to emit more NO_x, BC, PM_{2.5} and organic aerosol (OA) but less total hydrocarbon (THC) compounds than gasoline cars (Aakko-Saksa et al., 2020; Bahreini et al., 2012; Platt et al., 2013). However, we note that PM emissions of older direct-injection spark-ignition (DISI) gasoline fueled cars were also quite high (~10–16 mg m⁻³, Aakko-Saksa et al., 2014). Primary particulate tailpipe emissions from diesel vehicles have decreased as a result of after-treatment technologies, such as diesel oxidation catalyst (DOC) and especially BC through diesel particle filter (DPF) (Chirico et al., 2010; Gordon et al., 2014b; Wihersaari et al., 2020). However, these technologies do not remove NO_x and without the use of selective catalytic reduction (SCR), the emissions of NO_x are still higher than for gasoline vehicles (Kostenidou et al., 2021; Link et al., 2017). Even though catalysts and particle filters have helped to reduce fresh particulate emissions, the effect of aftertreatment on SecA is more difficult to assess since its chemical composition and physical properties depend e.g. on the precursor compounds such as ammonia, the type and composition of atmospheric oxidants, meteorological conditions, UV radiation, boundary layer mixing, as well as on the aging stage of aerosol.

Since the 2000s, the contribution of vehicle emissions to SecA has been studied with photochemical chambers such as oxidation flow reactors (OFR) (Zhang et al., 2024). These chambers allow for fast and on-site experiments simulating SecA formation through the rapid oxidation of precursor gases (Kang et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2024). A widely used OFR is the potential aerosol mass reactor (PAM). The PAM is a quartz or aluminum cylinder that contains a combination of UV lights to produce high amounts of oxidants that react with the gaseous precursor species in the sampled air and form SecA (Zhang et al., 2024). Due to the elevated oxidants concentration, the typical exposure in the chamber is of a few minutes, which is equivalent to hours to weeks in the atmosphere (Kang et al., 2007).

Previous studies using a PAM chamber to simulate SecA formation from vehicle exhaust emissions have shown the formation of organic and inorganic compounds (such as ammonium, nitrate, and sulphate) (Huang et al., 2024; Karjalainen et al., 2016; Simonen et al., 2019; Suarez-Bertoa et al., 2015; Timonen et al., 2017; Zhou et al., 2021). In these studies, the composition, number and mass concentration of SecA have depended greatly on the fuel used, the after-treatment devices, and the driving pattern and engine conditions. While many studies focused on either only gasoline or diesel vehicles, usually representing one Euro emission class, there are not many studies involving more recent cars, comparing modern and old cars, natural gas engines or hybrid vehicles. Additionally, it is difficult to compare the results between these studies because of the very different conditions used (driving cycle, chamber type and aging parameters, fuel used, or ambient/driving conditions). Furthermore, a large suite of state-of-the-art instrumentation is required to obtain a comprehensive understanding of vehicular emissions, making such investigations rare.

The aim of this study is to investigate the factors (driving condition, fuel, aftertreatment technology) driving the formation and chemical composition of aged aerosol from modern vehicles utilizing different fuels. The focus was on modern light-duty vehicles, even though older vehicles were also studied for comparison purposes. A chassis dynamometer campaign involving 7 different cars (Euro 4, 6b, 6d-Temp, and 6d gasoline, diesel, natural gas and hybrid vehicles) that were driven through the same real-driving-emissions simulating (RDEsim) cycle at

different ambient temperatures (23, 35 and -9 °C) was conducted. The novelty of this study lies in using modern cars that represented the most recent emission standard (Euro 6d), including hybrid cars for which there is very little data available, as well as driving a RDEsim cycle with temperatures beyond current Euro 6 regulations. A diverse range of instruments was employed to measure the chemical composition and physical properties of gaseous emissions, as well as fresh and aged aerosol emissions. This comprehensive approach aimed to provide a thorough characterization of exhaust emissions. The study was part of the PAREMPI project (parempi.eu), whose objective was to improve understanding of the contribution of the transport sector's emissions to ambient PM_{2.5} levels and their harmfulness. The link between the composition of vehicle exhaust secondary aerosol and their toxicology and health effects will be explored in a future study.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Vehicles, fuels and driving cycle

The measurement campaign was conducted at the Bosmal facility (Bielsko-Biala, Poland) from 3 to October 25, 2023, focusing on in-depth characterization of exhaust emissions of light-duty vehicles on simulated real-driving conditions. Tests were executed with chassis dyno AVL Zoellner 48" 4WD and Climatic Chamber WEISS WK 643 which can operate in the temperature range -35 to 60 °C.

Cars were chosen to cover the range of main older and most recent light-duty vehicles from popular brands with high sales in the EU. They include two older cars: a 2015 Euro 6b gasoline and a 2006 Euro 4 diesel; two newer ones: a 2023 Euro 6d gasoline and a 2022 Euro 6d diesel; two plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEV): a 2022 Euro 6d gasoline and a 2020 Euro 6d diesel; and a 2020 Euro 6d-TEMP compressed natural gas (CNG) car. The seven passenger vehicles selected are described in Table 1 with details on the engine, aftertreatments, Euro emissions class and production year. All cars had a direct injection system. The different exhaust after-treatment techniques are presented in Table 1. Shortly, diesel and gasoline particle filters (resp. DPF and GPF) reduce particle emissions. Three-way-catalysts (TWC) oxidize total hydrocarbons (THC) and CO to CO₂, and reduce NO_x in gasoline cars. Diesel oxidizing catalysts (DOC) reduce THC and CO levels by oxidation. Selective catalytic reduction (SCR) targets NO_x in diesel engines.

The gasoline provided by BOSMAL, Poland, met the European standard for gasoline (EN228), and the summer-grade diesel fuel met the European standard for automotive diesel fuel (EN590) (Tables S1 and S2). However, due to modest cold flow properties of the summer-grade diesel fuel, a winter-grade diesel fuel was provided for the measurements at -9 °C by VTT, Finland. The diesel fuel blend in the cold temperature measurements consisted of approx. 40 % summer-grade and 60 % winter-grade diesel fuel, as determined by density analyses.

The CNG car used compressed natural gas from the Finnish natural gas grid. This car primarily operated on CNG and used gasoline under certain conditions, such as during start-up or for temperatures below -10 °C, as specified by the manufacturer (Škoda, 2020). A small tank, less than 10 L, contained EN228 gasoline (VTT, Finland). The engine oils and their elemental composition used for each car are detailed in Table S3.

The real-driving emission (RDEsim) cycle was constructed based on actual on-road driving around Bielsko-Biala in normal ambient conditions and reproduced on a chassis dynamometer in the laboratory to simulate real driving in controlled, repeatable conditions at various temperatures. The RDEsim cycle consisted of different phases including the following characteristics: cold start, urban driving mixed with mountain and highway conditions, 10-min break (engine off) and extra-urban part (Table 2). Notably, several conditions were beyond current Euro 6 RDE emission standards. A maximum speed of >145 km/h was reached during the highway driving, and a slope variation allowed the simulation of mountain driving conditions. The RDEsim cycles were

Table 1

Used vehicles, fuel, engine, aftertreatment, emission level, model year and mileage.

Car	EU6b-G	EU4-D	EU6d-G	EU6d-D	PHEV-G	PHEV-D	EU6dT-CNG
Fuel type	Gasoline	Diesel	Gasoline	Diesel	Gasoline (PHEV)	Diesel (PHEV)	Natural gas (+gasoline)
Engine	4-cylinder 2.0 L	2.2 L D-4D turbocharged	1.0 L 3-cylinder turbo engine	1.5 L, 4-cylinder	1.6 L turbo 4-cylinder	2.0 L OM654 turbodiesel	1.5 L
After-treatment	TWC	DOC	TWC, GPF	DPF, DOC, SCR	TWC, GPF	DPF, DOC, SCR	TWC
Euro	6b	4	6d	6d	6d	6d	6d-TEMP
Year	2015	2006	2023	2022	2022	2020	2020
Mileage (km)	110 546	232 258	4162	12 482	16 067	22 597	39 406

PHEV = plug-in hybrid electric vehicle/TWC = three-way catalyst/GPF = gasoline particulate filter/DPF = diesel particulate filter/DOC = diesel oxidation catalyst/SCR = selective catalytic reduction.

Table 2

RDEsim test description including the duration (min), distance (km) of different phases and average speed (km/h) for each phase separately.

Cycle phase	Duration (min)	Distance (km)	Average speed (km/h)
Urban 1	13	5.6	24
Mountain	3	2.0	31
Highway	13	17.8	96
Urban 2	19	10.5	33
Parked	10	–	0.0
Rural	14	11.6	51
Total	72	48	Max. speed: 146

performed on a chassis dynamometer in a climatic chamber, allowing to set ambient temperatures to 23 °C as normal temperature, −9 °C as cold and +35 °C as hot conditions, which are beyond the current Euro 6 RDE boundary conditions.

This RDEsim driving cycle was repeated for each temperature and each car, so as to have at least 2 replications for each condition. The list of all performed tests, including date, identification number (ID) used within the project, car, temperature, and ID used in this paper is indicated in Table S4. Unfortunately, during the campaign, the soot-particle aerosol mass spectrometer (SP-AMS) was subject to instrumental failures, which resulted in the loss of seven days of measurements (10–18 October). Therefore, the aged aerosol data that this paper focuses on is available for 29/50 driving cycles, and the condition replications are detailed in Table S5.

2.2. Instrumental set-up

2.2.1. Set-up and instrumentation

The full measurement setup is shown in Fig. S1. Measurements of the exhaust sample consisted of primary regulated emissions by European Union (EU) including CO, CO₂, hydrocarbons, NO_x, particle mass and particle number concentration as well as a large setup of in-depth measurements of unregulated gaseous and particulate emissions. We use the term PM_{fresh} for fresh PM after cooling of the exhaust air and dilution, while PM_{aged} is used for PM after the PAM chamber, which includes both fresh PM and SecA mass formed in the chamber. The measurement instrument is shown after the term in brackets. The measurement set-up included a wide range of instruments for the characterization of both fresh and aged emissions (Table S6). Exhaust PM_{aged} samples were produced by a PAM chamber. Here we focus on the SP-AMS results located after the PAM chamber for the characterization of the chemical composition of PM_{aged}. SP-AMS and PAM are described in the following chapters.

The exhaust sample for the research instrumentation was taken through a Porous Tube Diluter (PTD, dilution ratio (DR) approximately 12). The PTD mimics atmospheric dilution conditions, allowing semi-volatile compounds to condense into particles (Rönkkö et al., 2006; Keskinen and Rönkkö, 2010). After the PTD, a residence time tube (RTT) that allows for mixing and stabilizing of the sample was used. The

sample was then divided into the characterizations of fresh and aged exhaust properties, and both had an ejector diluter (ED, DR of about 4 for the aged sample) to further dilute the sample, to avoid saturation of signal in instruments. The average total dilution ratios were approximately 120 for fresh exhaust aerosol and 90 for PAM aged exhaust aerosol samples. Diluted exhaust samples for the determination of particulate matter (abbreviated PM_{fresh,reg}) were taken from the constant volume sampling system (CVS ESU with dilution tunnel, HORIBA CVS 7400 S). For PM, a standard filter sampling system was used with 47 mm diameter TX40 filters. The measurement routine is described in Text S1.

2.2.2. Potential aerosol mass flow reactor

A PAM flow reactor (Aerodyne Research Inc, US; Kang et al., 2007; Lambe et al., 2011) was used to simulate atmospheric secondary aerosol formation. The PAM consisted of a cylindrical aluminum chamber (46 cm L x 22 cm W), with a volume of 13.3 L, equipped with two UV lights (wavelength of 185 nm) to produce concentrations of oxidants (OH, O₃, HO₂) that result in an atmospheric relevant particulate aging. One of the lamps was partially coated with fluoroelastomer heat-shrink tubing to reduce the strength of oxidation. The flow through the reactor during the campaign was on average 8.5 L min^{−1}, and the average residence time was 94 s. The relative humidity was monitored to stay above 30 % to ensure sufficient production of OH radicals. The aging of the aerosol is explained by oxidation reactions causing a change in chemical functionalization, such as oxygen addition which usually decreases volatility and increases condensation, or carbon loss which commonly increases volatility and evaporation (Lambe et al., 2012; Ortega et al., 2016). The aging time in the PAM was aimed to be at approximately 2–3 days based on previous studies by Tkacik et al. (2014), where a peak SOA production was achieved after 2–3 days, and by Ortega et al. (2016) that has shown a f44/f43 ratio (ratio of the m/z 44 (mainly CO₂⁺) to 43 (mainly C₂H₃O⁺) that gives an indication on the oxidation state of the particles) similar to ambient measurements at a traffic site for an aging between 0 and 3 days. However, during the experiments, the aging time varied significantly (0–10 days) due to important temporal variation of engine emissions of gaseous precursors (VOC, NO_x) consuming the oxidants, which affected the oxidants concentration and thus the OH exposure. Furthermore, O₃ is also formed in the PAM chamber, competing with the OH oxidation. However, O₃ is expected to have less influence on SOA formation than OH because the precursors present in exhaust emissions mainly consist of aromatics and saturated hydrocarbons that are generally not reactive towards O₃ (Tkacik et al., 2014).

The aging time in the reactor was estimated as the exposure to OH radicals. During the zero measurements, the OH exposure was monitored and adjusted by measuring CO decay, given by:

$$OH_{exp} = \frac{1}{k_{CO+OH}} * \ln \left(\frac{[CO]_i}{[CO]_f} \right) \quad (1)$$

where k_{CO+OH} is the reaction constant of CO with OH and is equal to $2.37 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecules}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Fiore et al., 2024). $[CO]_i$ and $[CO]_f$ are the initial and final concentrations of CO.

During the experiments, the OH exposure was modelled using the PAM chemistry model for oxidants (PAM_chem_V8). The inputs for the model were CO and NO_x concentrations, OH reactivity, relative humidity, and temperature of the sample, as well as the photon flux. CO and NO_x concentrations were measured with the FTIR, taking into account CO emitted from the tailpipe of the vehicle. The OH reactivity was calculated based on the concentrations of toluene, xylene and trimethylbenzene as these are the main contributors to OH reactivity from tailpipe emissions, measured by the VOCUS PTR-MS, and their reaction rates with OH (Shaw et al., 2020). The model does not consider the reactions of individual VOCs, but their contribution is estimated with a SO₂ concentration producing the same OH reactivity. The photon flux was estimated by reproducing the CO decay measurements with the model. The OH exposure was then converted to equivalent atmospheric photochemical age using the mean ambient OH concentration (1.5 10⁶ cm⁻³; Mao et al., 2009).

Note that the CO reaction rate with OH and the OH atmospheric concentration can be influenced by factors such as temperature, pressure, light intensity, or concentration of reactants, leading to significant variability based on geographic location, season, and time of day. As such, the values employed for these parameters provide only a rough estimate of particulate aging and, to better track particle aging in the SP-AMS, the f44/f43 ratio was also used.

LVOC (low volatile organic compounds) and PM_{fresh} losses in the reactor were both estimated to be low (see Text S2 and Fig. S2).

2.2.3. SP-AMS

A soot particle aerosol mass spectrometer (SP-AMS, Aerodyne Research Inc., USA; Onasch et al., 2012) was used to measure the mass concentration and chemical composition of the PAM aged submicron non-refractory particulate matter, NR-PM_{aged}(AMS). The SP-AMS consists of a high-resolution time-of-flight aerosol mass spectrometer (HR-ToF-AMS) to retrieve the chemical composition of non-refractory particulate species (total organic matter, NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻; for simplicity hereafter we will use abbreviations organics (Org), NO₃, NH₄, SO₄ and Cl for these ions) and of an additional ND-YAG laser for the analysis of refractory black carbon (rBC) and various metals. The instrument is further described in Karjalainen et al. (2016) and Timonen et al. (2017) and references therein. The instrument was operated in V mode with a time resolution set to 10 s to catch fast changes in the driving. However, the time resolution was increased to 20 s during the campaign due to data acquisition issues causing the software to crash. The particles were vaporized by both a tungsten vaporizer (600 °C) to analyze the non-refractory organic and inorganic species and the laser for rBC and metals. The SP-AMS data was analyzed using an AMS data analysis software (SQUIRREL v. 1.63B and PIKA v. 1.23B) in Igor Pro (Wavemetrics, Lake Oswego, OR). A collection efficiency (CE) of 1 was used since the same value has been employed in previous studies using SP-AMS for SecA measurements (Karjalainen et al., 2016; Timonen et al., 2017). This value may underestimate mass concentrations of uncoated, primary emissions but it is closer to the real value for heavily coated secondary aerosol. Moreover, CO₂ gas interferences were corrected using concentrations measured with the CO₂ analyzer placed next to the SP-AMS (Fig. S1).

A mass-based calibration of the SP-AMS was conducted prior to the campaign using dried size-selected particles (300 nm) of ammonium nitrate and ammonium sulphate. This calibration provided effective response factors for nitrate (IE NO₃) as well as relative ionization efficiencies of sulphate (RIE SO₄) and ammonium (RIE NH₄). These values were derived by converting the analyte signal into nitrate-equivalent mass concentrations. Additionally, the response of rBC was determined using a BC calibration. However, the rBC data was not included in this paper because the sizes of black carbon particles (approx. 30–100 nm) emitted by traffic mostly fall below the transmission efficiency of the SP-AMS (70–700 nm). Unfortunately, during the campaign, the SP-AMS was subjected to instrumental failures, following which the

filament was changed, and thus a second calibration was required. The second calibration was performed using the same method described above, and the obtained nitrate ionization efficiency values were 0.483 and 0.63 for the first and second calibrations, respectively. The RIE values used for ammonium and sulphate were 3.44 and 0.98, respectively. A default RIE value of 1.4 was used for organics.

2.2.4. Other instruments

Various gaseous compound emissions were measured by a Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) instrument, the portable BOB-1000 (A&D Technology, US). The IR absorbance spectrum (range 500–5000 cm⁻¹) is a sum of the spectra of all compounds of the exhaust sample, and their interferences are taken into account by calibrating the species present in exhaust gas. Generally, comparison of FTIR results with more traditional methods have shown satisfactory results for CO₂, CO, NO_x, while a higher deviation has been found for hydrocarbons (Giechaskiel and Clairrotte, 2021). The data was obtained in ppm_v (at 273.15K), which was then converted to mass emissions by using exhaust mass flow and distance driven over the test cycles.

Volatile organic compounds (VOC) were measured with a VOCUS proton-transfer-reaction mass spectrometer (PTR-MS) (Aerodyne Research US; Krechmer et al., 2018). In the VOCUS, water is ionized to produce H₃O⁺ ions. Proton transfer reaction from H₃O⁺ to gaseous compounds is fast and exothermic for most hydrocarbons. The VOCUS was operated at an E/N of 120 Td. It was calibrated at least twice per day with a calibration gas, a mixture of 14 common VOC.

An aethalometer (AE33, Magee Scientific, Slovenia; Drinovec et al., 2015) was used to measure the equivalent black carbon (eBC) concentrations in fresh emissions after the PTD + ED dilution. The AE33 measured light absorption through a sample laden filter at seven wavelengths between 370 and 950 nm with a time resolution of 1s.

Two electrical low-pressure impactors (ELPI+, Dekati, Finland; Järvinen et al., 2014; Keskinen et al., 1992) were used, one for fresh aerosol and the other for aged aerosol, allowing for the comparison of particle mass and number concentrations before and after the PAM. In the ELPI+, the exhaust particles are charged, classified into 14 size bins from 6 nm to 10 μm by a cascade impactor and detected with electrometers. The obtained current distribution is converted to number and mass distributions (see Text S3).

2.2.5. Emission factor calculations

Emission factors for the exhaust species measured by online instruments (e.g., FTIR, SP-AMS) were calculated per distance for each cycle. The following equation was used for calculation of emission factors over a time period from *i* to *j* (i.e., start to end of cycle):

$$EF_{(i-j)} = \frac{\sum_{n=i}^j (C \times DR \times Q_{exh})}{d} \quad (2)$$

Where EF is the emission factor for exhaust species in mg km⁻¹, C is the concentration in mg m⁻³ at 273.15 K, background-corrected for SP-AMS, DR is the dilution ratio calculated for each experiment, Q_{exh} is the exhaust flow in m³ s⁻¹ at 273.15 K, and d is the total distance travelled during the experiment in km.

Because of the OFR transfer functions, the temporal variation of PM_{aged} concentrations measured after the PAM does not reflect the rapid changes in the exhaust flow rate (Simonen et al., 2024). One way to take this phenomenon into account is by convoluting the exhaust flow rate (Q_{exh}) to simulate how it would be after the PAM. This was done by using the equations from Simonen et al. (2024) and the convolved Q_{exh} were used in Eq. (2). A comparison of emission factors calculated with both unconvolved and convolved Q_{exh} is presented in Fig. S3 and the average difference for both methods over all cycles was about 15 %.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Concentrations and chemical composition of aged PM

3.1.1. Enrichment of PM

Fig. 1 represents the PM₁ mass concentrations measured with the ELPI + for fresh and aged emissions and eBC measured with the AE33. The contribution of eBC to fresh PM emissions ranged 10–85 %. The highest fresh PM concentrations were measured for the Euro 4 diesel vehicle, followed by the CNG and Euro 6b gasoline cars. Similarly, the highest secondary emissions were observed for the EU4-D, EU6b-G and EU6dT-CNG vehicles. The enrichment ratio (in %) of PM was calculated as $\frac{(\text{aged} - \text{fresh})}{\text{fresh}} \times 100$ and ranged from 2 % for the Euro 4 diesel car to approximately 15000 % for Euro 6d gasoline. The low enrichment ratio for the Euro 4 diesel car could be explained by the high fresh PM emissions, especially of eBC, which does not react in the PAM chamber. On the other hand, the high enrichment ratio for EU6d-G is explained by the low fresh PM emissions and probable gaseous emissions reacting in the PAM. The corresponding mass concentration values can be found in Table S7. Table S8 presents the emission factors of gaseous and particulate emissions measured at different temperatures for all cars.

3.1.2. Temporal variation in secondary aerosol emissions during the driving cycle

The aged PM concentrations of organic matter (Org), nitrate (NO₃), ammonium (NH₄) and sulphate (SO₄) during the driving cycles are presented and discussed in this section. Fig. 2 shows the temporal variation of the chemical composition of aged submicron NR-PM emissions during a RDEsim cycle conducted at 23 °C for each of the seven cars (except for EU6d-G, the cycle shown was driven at 35 °C). Driving cycles at all temperatures are presented in Fig. S4. Fig. 2a shows the temporal variation of NR-PMaged (AMS) for the Euro 6b gasoline car and 3b. for the Euro 4 diesel car. These older cars are known to emit high concentrations of particulate compounds, as well as gaseous precursors needed for secondary aerosol formation (Aakko-Saksa et al., 2020; Saarikoski et al., 2024). The cold start at the beginning of the cycle for the Euro 6b gasoline produced high levels of nitrate (>8 mg m⁻³) and

organic matter (>15 mg m⁻³) and some ammonium likely due to the catalyst being cold and not oxidizing well the gaseous precursors of PMaged (Karjalainen et al., 2016; Kuitinen, 2021; Simonen et al., 2019). Maximum concentration of organics during the cold start were clearly higher than observed in a previous study using a Euro 5 gasoline car at 23 °C (approx. 0.2 mg m⁻³; Karjalainen et al., 2016) but lower than observed in a study using a Euro 6 gasoline vehicle (approx. 45 mg m⁻³; Simonen et al., 2019). However, we note that the aging (calculated based on OH exposure) was higher (8 days) in Karjalainen et al. (2016), and a different OFR chamber (TSAR) was used in Simonen et al. (2019), which both may have affected the SecA formation. While the measured organic matter concentration was rather low during the rest of the cycle for EU6b-G, nitrate and ammonium concentrations increased during accelerations and decelerations all through the cycle, as also seen in a previous study (Karjalainen et al., 2016). The highest ammonium (up to 4 mg m⁻³) and nitrate (over 30 mg m⁻³) emissions were seen during the rural phase at the end of the cycle. It could therefore impact the air quality particularly in rural areas. The concentration of all species dropped during the parking phase as the engine was stopped. The sum of nitrate and ammonium emissions over the whole cycle was higher than organics, as has been observed in a previous study using a 2016 GDI car (Peng et al., 2022). For the Euro 4 diesel car, measured concentrations of organic and inorganic particulate compounds were generally lower (<9 mg m⁻³) than for the Euro 6b gasoline car, but organic aerosol (2–8 mg m⁻³) concentrations remained elevated throughout the cycle. Other cycles for these cars (Fig. S4) show that the shape of the temporal variability is very similar among the cycles at 23°, while the concentration levels may vary. The temperature seems to play a role, in particular there is a strong increase in nitrate (approx. 14 mg m⁻³) and ammonium (approx. 2.5 mg m⁻³) during the cold start of Cycle 6 (EU4-D) at -9 °C. The systematic effect of temperature and aging will be discussed in Sect. 3.1.4.

To help understand these results, Fig. S5 shows the gaseous precursor (NO_x, NH₃, SO₂) volume mixing ratios during the same cycles as shown in Fig. 2. The Euro 6b gasoline car was observed to emit high levels of ammonia (NH₃) throughout the cycle (up to approx. 500 ppm), with also sporadic emissions of NO_x, leading to the formation of ammonium

Fig. 1. Fresh (in blue) and aged (in green) particulate emission factors measured by ELPI + before and after PAM, respectively, as well as eBC (in black) measured by AE33 before PAM. eBC was assumed unaltered in the PAM chamber. Bar graphs indicate the mean value of all cycles and error bars indicate standard deviation. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Temporal variation of aged PM concentration during driving cycles for each car: a. Euro 6b gasoline, b. Euro 4 diesel, c. Euro 6d gasoline, d. Euro 6d diesel, e. Euro 6d hybrid gasoline, f. Euro 6d hybrid diesel, and g. Euro 6d-T CNG. In panels a., b., c., d., and g., the shaded background corresponds to the driving phase (see legend). Panels e and f. have the same driving phases, but the gray background corresponds to the use of car mode combustion fuel. Note that the sub-panels have different ranges. Note that all cycles are at 23 °C except for the car EU6d-G due to the lack of precursor data, thus the cycle at 35 °C is shown here.

nitrate (NH₄NO₃). For the Euro 4 diesel on the other hand, NO_x emissions were much higher (about 1200 ppm), and SO₂ emissions were relatively high compared to the other cars (approx. 10 ppm). Since ammonia emissions of EU4-D were very low and ammonia reacts in priority with sulphate to form ammonium sulphate ((NH₄)₂SO₄) (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006), this led to less NH₄NO₃ formation than for EU6b-G.

In gasoline vehicles, ammonia can be formed in the TWC by

reduction of NO by hydrogen. H₂ and CO can be formed by a water-gas shift reaction and steam reforming reactions (Mejía-Centeno et al., 2007). In diesel vehicles, NH₃ can be formed in SCR systems for NO_x reduction, which uses a urea-based solution that produces ammonia as a reductant (Amanatidis et al., 2014; Suarez-Bertoa et al., 2014). The results showed that NO_x emissions were abundant in the case of an older diesel vehicle, therefore the formation of particulate ammonium nitrate was limited by the NH₃ levels. On the other hand, the older gasoline

vehicle emitted an abundant concentration of NH_3 , thus its NH_4NO_3 formation was limited by the lower NO_x emissions. In NH_3 -limited environment, such as urban areas, gasoline vehicles can provide NH_3 used in the formation of NH_4NO_3 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (Link et al., 2017), thereby increasing the formation of secondary aerosols (Sun et al., 2017).

Newer, Euro 6d gasoline and diesel cars (Fig. 2 c. & d.) show lower NR-PM_{aged} (AMS) concentrations during the cycles compared to the older cars, specifically of nitrate emissions for the gasoline car and of organic matter for the diesel car. However, both Euro 6d cars show a clear concentration increase at the cold start, mainly composed of organics for the gasoline car and of nitrate for the diesel one. This is likely related to higher precursor emissions at the start of the cycle, while only sporadic and low peaks during the rest of the drive were observed (Fig. S5 c. & d.). These results show that even though recent regulations have enabled an important reduction in secondary aerosol formation when driving the car, a cold start will still contribute to non-negligible quantities of aged PM. Other RDEsim cycles for EU6d-G (Fig. S4, cycle 8 and 9 at 23 °C and 35 °C) have very similar shapes and are quantitatively similar, while cycle 7 was also performed at 23 °C but NR-PM_{aged} concentrations are approximately 5 times lower. For EU6d-D, the cold start concentrations also differ from one cycle to the other, which could be explained by differences in the aging of the aerosol, and the cycle at -9 °C (cycle 13) surprisingly showed much lower nitrate.

Hybrid cars could decrease the total PM emissions from vehicles due to the partial use of an electrical motor. However, for PHEVs, frequent starting of internal combustion engine (ICE) may induce emissions, especially if the ICE starts during heavy driving conditions and the exhaust aftertreatment temperature has not reached optimal level yet (Melas et al., 2022; Sellieri et al., 2022; Suarez-Bertoa et al., 2021). Fig. 2 e and f. illustrate two examples of RDE cycles at 23 °C for Euro 6d PHEV gasoline and diesel cars. When the car uses electricity, emissions are close to zero (Fig. S5 e and f.) and thus NR-PM_{aged} concentrations are very low. However, it can be noted that the switch to the combustion engine (represented as gray background on the figure) produced cold start emissions at least as high as from non-hybrid Euro 6d cars. The use of electrical motor vs combustion engine depended on the driving mode, the state of the charge of the battery and the ambient temperature; the combustion engine was usually started for the first time during highway driving. The corresponding emission cycle of gaseous precursors (NH_3 , NO_x , SO_2) for the hybrid gasoline car (Fig. S5 e.) show that NH_3 emissions were significant and peaked at a similar level than EU6b-G (approx. 400 ppm) when the gasoline engine was on. In addition, NO_x increased drastically (>1800 ppm), but very shortly, when switching to combustion engine. These combined induced the production of particulate ammonium (>1.5 mg m^{-3}) and nitrate (>7 mg m^{-3}) in the PAM chamber (Fig. 2 e.). For the diesel car, gaseous NH_3 emissions were very low throughout the cycle (<10 ppm) when compared to the gasoline cars in this study. But they were sufficient that, when the diesel combustion engine was turned on and NO_x was emitted (~700 ppm), it also induced an increase in particulate nitrate (approx. 15 mg m^{-3}) and ammonium (>2 mg m^{-3}) formation (Fig. 2 f.). The regular switch between electric motor and combustion engine might therefore induce more PM_{aged} emission than vehicles using only combustion engines. These two cars had the most repetitions as they were a focus of the campaign, and the graphs obtained differ quite a lot (Fig. S4). This can be explained by the variation in the temperature, the aging in the chamber, as well as the use of electrical motor vs combustion engine.

Fig. 2 g shows particle mass emissions by component during a driving cycle for the natural gas car. The vehicle uses CNG as the main fuel, however it might use gasoline at the start of the drive and as necessary. Emissions of NO_x and NH_3 throughout the cycle (Fig. S5 g.) were seen to induce the formation of surprisingly high concentrations of nitrate (up to 20 mg m^{-3}) and ammonium (over 3 mg m^{-3}) for the CNG Euro 6d-T car throughout the cycle. These concentrations were notably higher than those obtained by Alanen et al. (2017) for an 2L passenger

car engine using natural gas as a fuel (<1 mg m^{-3} for both species). On the other hand, sulphate concentrations were lower (<0.1 mg m^{-3}) than those obtained by Alanen et al. (2017; about 0.5 mg m^{-3}). Organics concentrations were low during the cycle (about 1–2 mg m^{-3}) and similar to Alanen et al. (2017, around 1 mg m^{-3}), except for an observed significant increase of organic matter (up to > 15 mg m^{-3}) during the highway part of the driving cycle. This will be further discussed in Sect. 3.2.2. Note that when comparing with Alanen et al. (2017), the driving conditions and age in the PAM chamber (10.7 vs 3.6 days) were quite different, which likely explains some of the discrepancies between these studies. Other cycles using this car (Fig. S4) show a very similar shape in the variability, with some quantitative differences, except for cycle 28 at -9 °C which shows an additional increase in organics emission at the cold start of the cycle. This will also be explored in Sect. 3.2.2.

3.1.3. Emission factors of NR-PM_{aged} in relation to gaseous precursors

Emission factors (EF) were calculated for the aged PM species (see Sect. 2.2.5) and are given on Table S9 for each cycle. In addition, the emission factors were averaged per car and are presented for both gaseous precursors (NH_3 , NO_x , SO_2 , sum of hydrocarbons) and aged NR-PM₁ species in Fig. 3. The emission factors of primary gaseous and particulate compounds can be found in Table S8.

Fig. 3 a and b. highlight the significant quantitative differences between the vehicles for both precursor and aged PM emissions. The highest mean non-methane hydrocarbon (NMHC) emissions (~17–30 mg km^{-1}) were observed for EU6b-G, EU6dT-CNG and PHEV-G vehicles. Very high mean NO_x emissions (>0.75 g km^{-1}) were observed for the EU4-D vehicle, while they were on average more than 20 times lower for the other vehicles. The highest averaged ammonia emissions were observed for the Euro 6b-G and CNG cars (21–27 mg km^{-1}), as well as for the PHEV gasoline car (16 mg km^{-1}). The SO_2 emissions were quite high (15 mg km^{-1}) for the Euro 4 diesel car but remained rather low (<10 mg km^{-1}) for all other vehicles, as can be expected for low-sulfur fuels.

For the aged PM species (Fig. 3 b.), the highest emissions were observed for EU6b-G, EU4-D and EU6dT-CNG vehicles. In particular, the highest averaged organics emissions (2.5–3.6 mg km^{-1}) were obtained for EU4-D and EU6dT-CNG, while for the other cars, they fall below 1.7 mg km^{-1} . The highest nitrate (~10 mg km^{-1}) and ammonium (~1.3 mg km^{-1}) emissions were obtained for EU6b-G, while EU6dT-CNG also showed high (~4 mg km^{-1}) nitrate emissions. Higher nitrate production for gasoline and LPG (liquefied petroleum gas) vehicles has also been observed in a study involving Euro 5–6 cars (Link et al., 2017). For the Euro 6d cars (including the hybrids but excluding CNG), the mean aged PM emissions were low for all species (<2 mg km^{-1}). The sulphate emissions were very low (highest for Euro 4 diesel at 0.24 mg km^{-1}) and fairly similar for all vehicles, as could be expected based on the SO_2 emission levels. Despite these differences, the relative composition for all the vehicles (Fig. S6) was rather similar for EU6b-G, EU6d-D, PHEV-G and PHEV-D (68–77 % nitrate, 9–21 % organics, 10–13 % ammonium and 1–2 % sulphate). On the other hand, for EU4-D, EU6d-G and EU6dT-CNG, the percentage of organics was higher (61, 30 and 33 % respectively), and the percentage of nitrate lower (30, 52 and 57 % respectively).

As mentioned in Sect. 3.1.2, the formation of ammonium nitrate was limited by NH_3 in the case of diesel vehicles. From the graphs, these cars emitted very little NH_3 , while gasoline cars emitted less NO_x , but significant enough to induce NH_4NO_3 formation. Moreover, even though the Euro 4 diesel car overwhelmingly emitted the highest NO_x , it produced lower levels of ammonium nitrate than EU6b-G and EU6dT-CNG vehicles due to related ammonia emissions being negligible, which agrees with previous studies (Alanen et al., 2017). However, in the real atmosphere ammonium nitrate can be formed if ammonia is available from other sources like agriculture.

The newer Euro 6d gasoline and diesel cars showed, at 23 °C and on average, 94 % and 90 % decrease for gaseous precursors and aged

Fig. 3. Emission factors ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$) for a. gaseous precursors and b. aged aerosol species averaged over the RDEsim cycles at 23 °C. Error bars indicate the standard deviation of replications.

aerosol species respectively, compared to the older (Euro 4 & 6b) diesel and gasoline cars. Surprisingly, the CNG and hybrid gasoline cars NR-PMaged emissions were quite high, despite being equipped with the newest technology. This seems to be linked to the after-treatment-induced ammonia emissions. This correlates with Fig. 1 showing higher mass enrichment ratios for CNG than Euro 4 diesel from ELPI + results.

Based on Fig. 3, Euro 6b gasoline car and EU6dT-CNG show, on average, similar and high emission factors of NH_3 (27 and 21 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$ respectively), but the nitrate and ammonium formation is about 2 times higher for Euro 6b gasoline. To investigate these differences, in the next section the EFs for each individual cycle are compared, to evaluate the effect of the aging in the PAM chamber and of the temperature of the climatic chamber on the aged aerosol emissions.

3.1.4. Effect of photochemical age and temperature on aged aerosol emissions

Fig. 4 presents the EF of gaseous precursors and aged aerosol species for each cycle, performed at different age (OH exposure equivalent to 2.5–4.4 days) and different temperature (−9, 23 and 35 °C). We note

that due to instrument malfunction, there is a lack of repetition of the experiments under the same conditions (Table S5). Therefore, it might be difficult to highlight the effect specifically of the aging in the PAM and/or of the temperature in the climatic chamber on the emissions.

We first observe that for the cars that include at least one experiment at −9 °C (EU6b-G, EU6d-D, PHEV-G, PHEV-D and EU6dT-CNG), the total mean emission factors of gaseous precursors (SO_2 , NO_x , NH_3 , NMHC) are on average 57 % higher for cycles at −9 °C than 23 °C, especially for NMHC and NO_x . This would be expected, as catalysts are less efficient at lower temperatures (Platt et al., 2017). This difference did not directly translate for SecA, probably due to other conditions playing a role in its formation. There is a less apparent difference for gaseous precursors between 23 and 35 °C. For repetitions of the same car at 23 °C, the mean total EF for precursors varies 12 % on average.

An influence of the aging time in the chamber on the NR-PMaged EF was very difficult to identify. In addition to the equivalent atmospheric age, the ratio of f44 to f43 (more specifically CO_2^+ to $\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}^+$, obtained from the high-resolution AMS measurements) was used to infer for the aerosol age in the chamber. The ratio of NR-PMaged to gaseous precursors EF was plotted against the calculated age, as well as against f44/

Fig. 4. Cumulated emission factors (mg km^{-1}) of gaseous precursors and aged NR-PM₁ species for all experiments with car, age, f44/f43, and temperature indicated. Ages are only indicated when they could be calculated.

f43 to evaluate their tendencies. While there was no significant trend ($R^2 \geq 0.4$) towards an increase of the EF ratio with increasing age in the chamber for the cars, there was a significant decreasing trend for EU6d-G. However, there was a significant trend of increasing EF ratio with increasing f44/f43 for the EU6b-G, EU6d-D, PHEV-G, and EU6dT-CNG (R^2 of 0.85, 0.72, 0.88 and 0.87 respectively). There was no significant trend for EU6d-G and PHEV-D, and not enough data points for EU4-D. This indicates that, for most cars, SecA formation increases with

particle aging in the conditions of the performed experiments.

There was a clear effect of cold conditions compared to warm conditions on gaseous precursors emissions, but the equivalent age in the chamber did not strongly affect the aged aerosol, probably due to the uncertainties in correctly modelling it. Higher aged aerosol formation was however associated with a higher aerosol age (estimated using the ratio of CO_2^- to $\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}^+$) for some of the cars. These effects remain difficult to evaluate due to the lack of repetitions. Also, we note that

these are average values over whole cycles, the aging during a cycle could vary considerably, in particular during the cold start.

While the effect of aging was difficult to evaluate, it was clear that it is a variable to consider for the interpretation of the results, and for the capacity of reproducing real-world emissions. Moreover, the comparison between different vehicles and different temperatures would be more fruitful if aging time was more stable and easier to adjust.

3.2. Detailed chemical composition of aged organic aerosol

3.2.1. Aged organic aerosol mass spectra

This section discusses in more detail aged organic aerosol. The SP-AMS measures high-resolution mass spectra allowing the identification of the main fragments for each m/z based on their chemical formulas. These can be further separated into the following hydrocarbons classes: $\text{CH} = \text{C}_x\text{H}_y^+$, $\text{CHO1} = \text{C}_x\text{H}_y\text{O}^+$, $\text{CHOgt1} = \text{C}_x\text{H}_y\text{O}_z^+$, $z > 1$, $\text{CHN} = \text{C}_x\text{H}_y\text{N}^+$, $\text{CHO1N} = \text{C}_x\text{H}_y\text{ON}_p$, $\text{CHOgt1N} = \text{C}_x\text{H}_y\text{O}_z\text{N}_p^+$, $z, z > 1, N_p^+$.

Fig. 5 presents the mass spectra in unit mass resolution colored based on the classes of the main fragments identified for each m/z and averaged over one cycle for each of the seven cars. The experiments considered here are the same as for Fig. 2. Notable m/z and their dominant fragment(s) are indicated on the figure. The mass spectra for Euro 6b gasoline, Euro 6d gasoline and diesel, and both hybrid cars are similar and representative of secondary organic aerosol (SOA), with important fragments at m/z 43 and 44 mainly attributed to $\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}^+$ and CO_2^+ respectively, linked to the fragmentation of oxygenated compounds. An important fragment present in all mass spectra is C_6H_5 at m/z 77, which originates from aromatic compounds (McLafferty and Turccek, 1993). For these cars, oxygenated hydrocarbon fragments (classes CHO1 and CHOgt1) are therefore dominant, as can be seen on Fig. S7, with a total contribution of about 70 %. On the other hand, the hydrocarbons (CH family) contribute about 20–25 %, corresponding to fresh PM_{10} or fragments from SOA.

The mass spectrum for the Euro 4 diesel also shows high m/z 43 and 44 peaks, as well as a non-negligible contribution from the CH family (about 40 %, Fig. S7). However, dominant fragments also include m/z 77, m/z 141 and m/z 170 which were respectively attributed mainly to C_6H_5^+ , $\text{C}_5\text{H}_3\text{NO}_4^+$ and $\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{NO}_4^+$ (Fig. S8). To our knowledge, no similar profile exists in the literature for aged organic aerosol from diesel car exhaust. Fig. S7 shows a more important contribution from N-containing families than for the other cars (about 17 % vs 2–9 %). Therefore, the concentration of particulate organic nitrate (pON) measured by the AMS as inorganic nitrate was estimated using the $\text{NO}^+/\text{NO}_2^+$ ratio (Day et al., 2022; Farmer et al., 2010; Graeffe et al., 2023) for cycle 4 and is detailed in Text S4. Organic nitrate fragments were estimated to contribute 0–41 % of total measured nitrate during this cycle. This corresponded to a pON concentration of 0.28 mg m^{-3} on average and up to 1.88 mg m^{-3} . The particulate organic nitrate could result from the OH oxidation of primary compounds such as hydrocarbons, and the reaction of the peroxy radicals formed with the high NO_x emissions. Correctly attributing nitrate is important, as organic nitrate might not have the same properties and role in atmospheric chemical reactions as inorganic nitrate.

The mass spectrum for CNG displays a profile similar to fresh gasoline emissions (Mohr et al., 2009) and hydrocarbon-like organic aerosol (HOA) obtained from source apportionment studies, which are usually related to fresh traffic emissions. In fact, it contains high C_xH_y fragments at m/z 41 (C_3H_5^+), 43 (C_3H_7^+), 55 (C_4H_7^+), 57 (C_4H_9^+), 69 (C_5H_9^+), 71 ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}^+$) and 85 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}^+$) (Canagaratna et al., 2007; Crippa et al., 2013). Fig. S7 also shows the dominant (~70 %) contribution from hydrocarbon fragments (CH family), and the weaker (~30 %) contribution from oxygenated compounds (CHO1 and CHOgt1). SOA emissions from the CNG car are further discussed in the following section.

3.2.2. Impact of CNG vs gasoline usage on SOA

The driving cycle of the CNG car at 23°C (Fig. 2 g.) shows that aged

organic aerosol emission increases during the highway phase of the cycle. Fig. 6a presents a driving cycle for this car at -9°C , showing an additional peak of organics during the cold start ($>30 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$). Fig. 6b links the first peak to the emission of aromatic VOCs (benzene, toluene, xylenes, trimethylbenzenes) at the start of the cycle and their subsequent oxidation in the PAM. The mass spectrum during this first peak is indeed representative of SOA with high f43 and f44 and dominance of the organic group CHO_1 (Fig. 6c.). On the other hand, the second peak, during the highway phase, shows a mass spectrum composed mainly of the CH family and similar to an HOA profile, thus representative of fresh PM emissions (Fig. 6d.). Moreover, it is not linked to an increase in BTEX emissions (Fig. 6b.). The high concentrations during the cold start could arise from the use of gasoline triggered at low temperatures, as well as a poorer combustion efficiency and the catalyst not fully functioning at these temperatures (Platt et al., 2017). On the other hand, the peak during the highway phase could be linked to lubricant oil emissions, which increase at higher engine speed as oil consumption increases (Apicella et al., 2024). These emissions are composed mainly of cycloalkanes (Worton et al., 2014), less reactive towards OH than aromatics, which could explain their low oxidation in the PAM. Their SOA formation potential might be lower, but these emissions should still be taken into account to improve air quality in high traffic areas.

4. Conclusions

This work presents the chemical composition of aged aerosol from light-duty vehicle exhaust. The studied passenger cars were modern and represented various technological approaches, i.e. different fuels, plug-in hybrid vehicles (PHEV), and different exhaust aftertreatments, thereby being highly relevant for current and future traffic fleets in Europe. The potential of exhaust emissions to form secondary aerosols was studied using the same set-up and real-driving emission simulation cycle for all vehicles to ensure comparability.

Results indicate that secondary aerosol (SecA) emissions surpassed fresh aerosol emissions for all cars, except for Euro 4 diesel, partly due to its high primary eBC emissions. For all cars, the driving style highly impacted the emission of gaseous precursors and the subsequent SecA formation. While the Euro 6d cars showed much lower SecA emissions throughout the cycle, their cold start emissions were still comparable to emissions from older vehicles. In particular for PHEV, SecA emissions were significant when starting up the combustion engine, which, depending on the driving mode used and the length of the drive, could impact the air quality in urban and residential areas. The aftertreatment also had a significant impact on the emissions. Indeed, while these technologies have drastically reduced the emissions of fresh particles and of gaseous compounds such as NO_x , three-way-catalysts and selective catalytic reduction devices were observed to emit non-negligible amounts of NH_3 which can react with NO_x to form NH_4NO_3 .

In general, higher gaseous precursors emissions led to higher aged aerosol emissions, but these chemical processes are not always linear. For example, higher NO_x emissions for the Euro 4 diesel car did not lead to higher nitrate production, due to the low ammonia emissions limiting the reaction in this case. In real ambient air however, ammonia might be available from gasoline and CNG cars, as well as from other sources. The relationship between primary and secondary emissions was also reflected on the aged aerosol oxidation state, estimated from its f44/f43 ratio.

A more detailed study of aged organic aerosol using the high-resolution mass spectra for the different cars showed that it contained high amounts of fragments from oxidized compounds, as expected for SOA. However, the CNG car showed a mass spectrum containing mainly hydrocarbon-like OA, which could be associated with an emission of primary OA from lubricant oil during the highway driving phase. In addition, this analysis showed the presence of significant amounts of organic nitrate in the aged aerosol for the Euro 4 diesel car, which had not been quantified before in vehicle exhaust studies and could impact

Fig. 5. Family-colored unit mass resolution mass spectra of aged NR-PM1 averaged over one cycle for each car. Main mass spectra are zoomed between m/z 10–80, while full spectra are shown as inset figures. Notable m/z are indicated on the figure.

Fig. 6. Aged PM concentration during the cycle driven by the CNG car at -9°C (cycle 28), b. BTEX (benzene, toluene, xylenes, trimethylbenzenes) emissions during this cycle, c. OA mass spectrum during the first OA peak, and d. OA mass spectrum during the second OA peak.

atmospheric chemistry differently than inorganic nitrate.

This study indicates that it is important to also consider secondary aerosol and its precursors for current and future emissions regulation as well as for reduction technologies, to best mitigate atmospheric PM in urban traffic-influenced areas. Future technological improvements should focus on reducing cold start emissions, lubricant oil emissions in CNG cars, and a better treatment of NH₃ in the TWC and SCR after-treatment devices. The determination of SecA formation potential was possible but challenging, and further studies are needed with similar measurement protocols. In addition, this study highlights the large differences between the cars, which underlines the need for further studies to generate solid literature on the SecA formation potential of vehicular exhaust emissions. Future studies should include hybrid cars and longer drives to confirm the effect of the engines switch on aged aerosol emissions. This study was done on vehicles typical for Europe and based on EU emissions standards, thus it would be fruitful to perform similar work representative of other regions in the world, by using different vehicles and atmospheric conditions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Leila Simon: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Luis Barreira:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Katariina Kylämäki:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Sanna Saarikoski:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Minna Aurela:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Delun Li:** Investigation. **Anssi Järvinen:** Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Hannu Kuutti:** Investigation. **Wojciech Honkisz:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Milja Jäppi:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Laura Salo:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Matti Rissanen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Tereza Červená:**

Methodology, Investigation. **Michal Vojtšek:** Methodology, Investigation. **Jan Topinka:** Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Piotr Bielaczyc:** Supervision, Resources. **Topi Rönkkö:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Päivi Aakko-Saksa:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Hilkka Timonen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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